

ORGANIZATION OF NUTRITION FOR THE ELDERLY

Muzafarova Kholida Mukhsinovna*

Kurbanov Murad Toshpulatovich**

Muzafarova Dildora Mukhsinovna***

* Doctoral Researcher, Bukhara Institute of Engineering and Technology, Bukhara, Republic of Uzbekistan

** Associate Professor, Candidate of Technical Sciences, Bukhara Institute of Engineering and Technology, Bukhara, Republic of Uzbekistan

*** Student, Bukhara Institute of Engineering and Technology, Bukhara, Republic of Uzbekistan

ABSTRACT *Excessive high-calorie diet of the majority of the world's elderly has negative effects on the aging process (overweight, obesity, metabolic syndrome).*

At the same time, an excessive decrease in the amount of calories (malnutrition) leads to a physiologically unreasonable consumption of not only carbohydrates and fats, but also the body's own proteins, and a decrease in skeletal muscle mass. As a result, work capacity decreases, immune deficiency develops, dystrophic processes develop, and aging is activated.

KEY WORDS: *Aging and senescence, Malnutrition, Healthy nutrition, Protein synthesis, Protein needs, Diet, Gerodiet products.*

INTRODUCTION

Currently, the number of pensioners in Uzbekistan is 6.8% of the total population, by 2030 this figure will reach 11.6%, and in 2050 the number of pensioners in the country will reach 19.4%, according to a report by HelpAge International.

The number of elderly people in Uzbekistan by 2050 will reach 19.4% of the total population in this country, according to the results of the Global AgeWatch Index 2014, compiled by the international charitable organization HelpAge International with the support of the UN and published on the International Day of Older Persons, which is celebrated on October 1.

Issues related to aging and senescence have been of interest to mankind since ancient times, and even today there are enough problems in this regard. Issues that have been considered for several centuries before and after our era are aimed at living a healthy life for many years with all vital functions preserved. Most of the efforts in this direction did not have significant results in their time because they did not have a scientific basis.

There should be more than 600 nutrients in the human diet on a regular basis. About 95% of them have therapeutic and preventive properties. The dietary qualities of the product depend on their composition and ratio.

Expert analysis shows that if 17% of the world's population is chronically undernourished, 25% of the world's population may suffer from hunger in the next decade. About 5 million people die from malnutrition every year.

Every third cancer, every second cardiovascular disease is caused by poor diet.

Creation of new products, enriched with functional ingredients, with balanced products, is of particular importance in the rational healthy diet of the population. In accordance with the Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4887 of November 10, 2020 "On Amendments and Additions to the Decision "On Additional Measures to Ensure Healthy Nutrition of the Population", according to the World Health Organization, follow the norms and rules of physical activity and nutrition not doing it, excessive consumption of food and sweets with a lot of salt, sugar, and fat content, as a result of not consuming minerals, causes the development of a number of diseases that lead to premature death of a person, such as cardiovascular, endocrine, and malignant tumors.

The main difference of this concept is to create natural functional food products.

The purpose of the state policy in the field of healthy nutrition is to maintain and strengthen the health of the population, and prevent diseases.

The main directions of the state policy in the field of healthy nutrition:

- creation of qualitatively new food production technology, including: consumer goods for different age groups of the population, including children and the elderly;
- therapeutic and prophylactic products to prevent various diseases and strengthen the protective functions of the body, reduce the risk of exposure to harmful substances;
- food products for some groups of the population in extreme conditions and military personnel;
- enrichment of products with micro- and macroelements, expansion of production of biologically active additives.

The structural and metabolic changes that develop in the elderly people require a particularly careful approach. It is based on the scientific principles of organizing a balanced diet.

These include:

- the energy balance of food with actual energy consumption of the body;
- the preventive approach of nutrition not only to atherosclerosis, but also to other common pathologies of old age - obesity, diabetes, hypertension, cancer, osteoporosis, etc.;
- compatibility of the chemical composition of food with age-related changes in metabolism;
- balance of diets for all important nutritional factors;
- rationalization of nutrition of elderly people.
- use of food products and dishes that are very easily affected by the action of digestive enzymes, assimilation processes.

It should be noted that with aging there is a decrease in protein synthesis due to a decrease in synthesis processes associated with growth. At the same time, the decrease in synthesis is accompanied by the cessation of protein degradation

processes. According to Grigorov Yu.G., "The re-synthesized protein molecule lives longer, the half-life increases. Thus, the decrease in synthesis is compensated by a decrease in protein breakdown, and the balance is maintained, although much lower than in youth. All this indicates that the aging body's need for dietary protein decreases.

The legality of this conclusion is also confirmed by data on the use of high-protein food in the elderly, which is accompanied by a deterioration in general well-being, excretory function of the kidneys, and the functional state of the cardiovascular system. In general, the question of the daily protein requirement of the elderly cannot be considered sufficiently studied. For example, in Germany, 78 g of protein or 13% of calories per day is recommended for the elderly. In Russia, the protein norm for elderly people is slightly higher and makes up 14% of daily calories.

Along with the emergence of a quantitative need for proteins, their qualitative composition becomes especially important depending on age.

A recent review of the literature suggests that 60% of the daily protein needs of older adults come from animal products. At the same time, with aging, the percentage of protein in vegetable products should increase slightly (additional effect of vitamins and fiber). This conclusion is based, in part, on an analysis of data obtained from studies of the nutrition of long-lived people. In older people, it was distinguished by a clear direction of milk and vegetables and strict adherence to national customs. Recommended values of protein consumption in the diet of elderly people are presented in the table.

Recommended daily protein intake

Age groups		Recommended protein intake, g	
		total	Including animal
Men	60-74	85	44
	75 and older	75	38

Women	60-74	78	40
	75 and older	68	34

An analysis of the actual diet of the elderly showed that their total protein was deficient in leucine, methionine, valine, arginine, glycine and aspartic acid.

Until now, there is so little information about the creation of gerodietic products both in our country and abroad that it is not necessary to talk about it as a direction of serious technological developments. At the same time, the experience gained by specialists in the fields of medicine, dietology and gerontology allows us to conclude that gero-diet products should soon occupy a worthy place in the diet of the population of our Republic. The need to create them is determined by life itself.

In the development and creation of functional food products for gerodietetic purposes, it is necessary to know the chemical composition of raw materials, nutritional value and special processing techniques.

It is a very difficult task to achieve a balance in the chemical composition only at the expense of their natural reserves when creating food products for the elderly and old age. The most promising solution to this problem is to implement the advantages of several directions at the same time.

Modern ideas about ways to create Gerodiet products can be divided into the following areas:

The first is to create fully balanced products that fully meet the needs of the elderly's body.

The second is products designed for nutritional correction. This direction involves the creation of products enriched with one or more nutrients.

The third is food modules (premixes), which allow correcting both one meal and daily nutrition at the same time. This group of supplements, in addition to enriching the diet, allows for targeted control of the synergistic properties of individual components of the product.

In conclusion, the urgent task facing all sectors of the food industry is to expand the range of food products for herodietic purpose and to improve the technology by using natural, inexpensive raw materials and materials that meet the requirements of nutrition.

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